

PIN-CONTACT FAILURE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

C. T. Sun and P. S. Wu

School of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Purdue University, West Lafayette, IN 47907-1282, U. S. A.

ABSTRACT

Pin-contact failure in composite laminates was investigated. The experimental part of this research involved the use of a contact test in which a steel pin was pressed against the straight edge of a composite laminate. To identify the damage modes and failure mechanisms, several specimens were loaded to various levels and then sectioned for microscopic observation. It was found that failure initiated at the edge near the flat surfaces at 80-85% of the ultimate contact load. The failure mode in the 0° -plies resembles the kink band observed in compression failure in unidirectional composites. Stress analysis results indicated that elasticity is not adequate to predict the contact strength of the laminate. Thus, plastic behavior of the composite must be accounted for. In addition, the contact friction between the pin and the composite is also important to the modeling. An approximate 3-D finite element analysis was performed on the pin-contact problem. Using the elastic-plastic analysis result in conjunction with buckling criterion, the failure initiation due to pin-contact was successfully predicted.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanically fastened joints are commonly used in composite parts. To utilize the full potential of these materials as structural elements, the strength and failure behavior of bolted joints must be understood. Considerable studies in this topic have been reported [1-7]. Most of the earlier work [1, 2] concentrated on experimental investigation. Later, some authors [3, 4] used two-dimensional stress fields and semi-empirical models to estimate the joint strengths. Marshall et al [5] performed a three-dimensional stress analysis, but no failure criterion was introduced. Recently, Chang et al [6] developed new pin and bolt bearing tests to characterize bearing failure mechanisms. However, the damage initiation mechanism was not fully explained.

In the present study, a pin-contact test is used to characterize the contact damage process in the composite laminate. This test involves using a steel pin to press against the straight edge of the laminate to produce contact failure. An approximate three-dimensional finite element model is adopted to obtain through-the-thickness stresses. Plastic behavior of the composite is included to obtain more accurate stress distributions. Finally, an elastic-plastic microbuckling criterion is employed to predict the onset of contact failure.

EXPERIMENT

SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TEST PROCEDURE

Two laminate configurations, $[0/90]_{10S}$ and $[90/0]_{10S}$, were fabricated from graphite/epoxy AS4/3501-6 composite. Specimens approximately 60 mm long and 45 mm wide were cut by a water-jet. Subsequently, the laminate edges were examined by X-radiography. Smoothness of the straight edge surface is critical to the test; so it was further polished with 600-grit sand paper to ensure good flatness.

A schematic diagram of the experimental setup for the pin-contact test is shown in Fig. 1. In the test, a load was applied through the hardened steel pin 12.7 mm in diameter, and the specimen was clamped on its lower portion. All specimens in this study were loaded at a stroke rate of 0.1 mm/min on an MTS machine. Six replicas were tested beyond their peak load. Due to the clearances of MTS machine and fixtures, the measured displacement is larger than the real one, but the load value is accurate.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of pin-contact test

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A typical load-displacement curve is shown in Fig. 2. The peak load is easy to identify. However, the damage initiation load level is hard to define. Consequently, microphotographs were used to investigate the contact damage process. A typical microphotograph of the cross section in a specimen loaded beyond peak contact load is shown in Fig. 3. The failure mode in the 0° -plies resembles the kink band observed in compression failure in unidirectional composites.

To further investigate the location and load level of the onset of failure, specimens loaded up to different load levels were sectioned and examined. Figure 4 shows the microphotograph of the $[0/90]_{10S}$ specimen loaded to 90% of the ultimate load. It is evident that failure initiates at the outermost 0° -ply near the contact surface and propagates at an angle about 50° to the loading direction. The major failure mode appears to be fiber microbuckling in the 0° -plies.

Table 1 summarizes the experimental results for both laminates. It is seen that the $[90/0]_{10S}$ laminate sustains slightly higher strength than the $[0/90]_{10S}$ laminate. The phenomenon was also noticed by previous researchers [5-7]. According to load-displacement curves and microphotographs, we suggest that failure initiates between 80-85% of the ultimate load.

Figure 2. Typical load-displacement curve

Figure 3. Photograph of the damage in the cross section of $[0/90]_{10s}$ loaded beyond the peak contact load

Figure 4. Photograph of the damage in the cross section of $[0/90]_{10s}$ loaded to 90% of the peak contact load

Table 1. Experimental Results

Load (KN)	$[0/90]_{10s}$	$[90/0]_{10s}$
Ultimate Load	10.2	10.7
Initiation Load	8.2-8.7	8.6-9.1

STRESS ANALYSIS

From the results in Fig. 3 and 4, contact failure is seen to propagate in the thickness-direction as contact load increases. This indicates that out-of-plane stresses are important in failure progression. Therefore, 3-D stress analyses must be performed. To simplify the 3-D analysis, a 2-step approximate 3-D finite element analysis was used in this study.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A 2-D finite element analysis is first performed on the contact problem. The specimen and pin are modeled in the X-Y plane by 8-node isoparametric plane stress and plane strain elements, respectively, as depicted in Fig. 5. Symmetrical boundary conditions enable construction of one-half the model. At the center of pin, a load in the X-direction is applied, while at the bottom end of the specimen, clamp boundary condition is assumed. The commercial finite element code ABAQUS is used. Non-penetration condition at the contact region is imposed through the use of interface elements. The effect of contact friction in the X-Y plane is neglected. Table 2 lists the material properties. The pin is regarded as elastic. Effective elastic constants derived from [0/90] sublaminates are used for the laminate [8].

An associated 3-D model is established by extending the previous 2-D mesh in the thickness direction. Due to symmetrical boundary conditions, only one-quarter of the composite laminate is modeled. The 20-node isoparametric brick element in ABAQUS is used.

Through the 2-D finite element results, the in-plane displacements of nodes on the contact region are obtained and imposed on the corresponding 3-D model with the Z-direction displacements of these nodes set free except for those on the contact surface, which are set equal to zero. This condition indicates that friction prevents movement of the contact nodes in the Z-direction.

Table 2. Material Properties

Material	Material Constants
Steel Pin	$E = 200 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.3$, $\sigma_y = 1380 \text{ MPa}$
Graphite/Epoxy Composite Lamina	$E_1 = 140 \text{ GPa}$, $E_2 = 10 \text{ GPa}$, $E_3 = 10 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{12} = 7 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{13} = 7 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{23} = 3.5 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.29$, $\nu_{13} = 0.29$, $\nu_{23} = 0.47$

COMPOSITE ELASTIC-PLASTIC MATERIAL MODEL

If 80% peak load is utilized in the elastic analysis, the resulting stresses would significantly exceed the ply strengths of the composite. To correct this phenomenon, plastic behavior of the composite must be accounted for. In this study, a 3-D plasticity model for composites proposed by Sun and Chen [9] is adopted in the elastic-plastic analysis. Assuming transverse isotropy and that plasticity in the longitudinal (x_1) deformation is negligible, we have the plastic potential as

$$2f(\sigma_{ij}) = (\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + 4\sigma_{23}^2 + 2a_{66}(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2), \quad (1)$$

where a_{66} is an anisotropy coefficient which can be determined by off-axis compression tests. For the AS4/3501-6 composite, the effective stress-effective plastic strain data for a number of off-axis angles is collapsed into a single curve for $a_{66} = 2.5$ as shown in Fig. 6. The master effective stress ($\bar{\sigma}$)-effective plastic strain ($\bar{\epsilon}^p$) curve can be fitted with a power law as

Figure 5. 2-D finite element mesh

Figure 6. Effective stress-effective plastic strain curves

$$\bar{\epsilon}^p = A(\bar{\sigma})^n, \quad (2)$$

where A is $1.048 \times 10^{-15} \text{ (MPa)}^{-n}$ and n is equal to 5.2.

Commercial finite element code ABAQUS incorporating the present plastic potential function together with the associated flow rule is used to perform elastic-plastic analysis of the composite. Figure 7 shows the stress distributions in the outermost 4 plies at 80% peak contact load. It indicates that through-the-thickness shear stress (τ_{xz}) decays in the X and Z directions, while the compressive normal stress (σ_{xx}) is more uniform. The maximum values of both stresses are inside the outermost 0° ply. Based on experimental inspections and numerical results, the critical volumes for damage initiation in both laminates as shown in Fig. 8 are chosen. Stresses within this volume are averaged to predict the onset of contact failure.

Figure 7. Typical stress distributions in $[0/90]_{10s}$ laminate at 80% peak contact load

FAILURE PREDICTION

FIBER MICROBUCKLING MODEL

From the contact test results, microbuckling is believed to be the primary damage initiation mechanism that triggers subsequent failures. Thus, a fiber microbuckling failure model proposed by Sun and Jun [10], which includes non-linear matrix stress/strain behavior, is adopted to predict the contact failure initiation. The microbuckling failure model predicts the compressive strength of a fiber composite to be

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{G_m^{ep}}{1 - c_f} \quad (3)$$

where c_f is the fiber volume fraction and the matrix elastic-plastic shear modulus G_m^{ep} is given by

$$G_m^{ep} = \left[\frac{1}{G_m} + \frac{9\theta^2}{(\beta^2 + 3\theta^2)H_p} \right]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

in which $\theta = \frac{\tau_{cr}}{\sigma_{cr}}$, $\beta = \frac{1}{\alpha c_f + c_m}$, $\alpha = \frac{E_f}{E_{ms}}$, E_f is the fiber modulus of elasticity, E_{ms} is the secant matrix modulus and H_p is the shear dependent tangent modulus of uniaxial stress/plastic strain curve. In the present application, $\tau = \tau_{xz}$.

The solution for composite microbuckling stress σ_{cr} is found numerically. For a given shear stress τ_{cr} at failure, the composite compressive stress σ is increased incrementally. If the updated σ used in Eqn (4) is equal to the calculated σ in Eqn (3), then critical buckling stress σ_{cr} is obtained. At each step, the value of α , and thus, β , are updated. For various τ_{cr} values assumed, composite critical compressive stress (σ_{cr}) versus critical shear stress (τ_{cr}) curve at fiber microbuckling is constructed and shown as the solid line in Fig. 9.

Figure 8. Schematic diagram showing the location and size of critical volume for contact damage initiation

DAMAGE INITIATION PREDICTION

The average compressive stress (σ_{xx}) and through-the-thickness shear stress (τ_{xz}) in the critical volume are obtained from the approximate 3-D finite element analysis. These average stresses can be plotted as shown in Fig. 9 as the contact load increases. When this curve meets the fiber microbuckling curve, compressive failure in the outermost 0°-ply would occur and contact failure would initiate. From Fig. 9, it is seen that the failure compressive stresses for the two laminates are different.

Figure 9. Loading paths of the critical volume

Figure 10. Compressive stress versus applied load

The average compressive stress in the critical volume is related to the contact load as shown in Fig. 10. According to present calculations, contact failure initiation loads for $[0/90]_{10S}$ and $[90/0]_{10S}$ laminates are 8.1 KN and 8.2 KN, respectively. These values in general agree with the experimental estimations in Table 1. Moreover, the fact that the $[90/0]_{10S}$ laminate has a higher contact strength than the $[0/90]_{10S}$ laminate is also correctly predicted.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the experiment for determining failure initiation in a composite laminate contacting a steel pin has been conducted. In addition, a finite element simulation based on elastic-plastic material model was performed. According to the comparison between the analytical and experimental results, the following conclusions are reached.

1. Contact damage initiates at the edge near the flat surfaces at the load level of 80-85% ultimate load and fiber microbuckling appears to be the primary failure mode.
2. 3-D stress analysis is necessary to explain contact failure.
3. Plastic behavior of the composite must be included in the stress analysis.
4. The proposed microbuckling criterion can predict the contact failure initiation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the Office of Naval Research through Grant No. N00014-J-1666 to Purdue University. Dr. D. S. Y. Rajapakse was the technical monitor.

REFERENCES

1. W. J. Quinn and F. L. Matthews, The Effect of Stacking Sequence of the Pin-Bearing in Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastic. *J. Composite Materials*, **11**, 139-145 (1977).
2. T. A. Collings, The Strength of Bolted Joints in Multi-Directional CFRP Laminates. *Composites*, **8**, 43-54 (1977).
3. T. A. Collings, On the Bearing Strengths of CFRP Laminates. *Composites*, **13**, 241-252 (1982).
4. F. K. Chang, R. A. Scott and G. S. Springer, Failure Strength of Nonlinear Elastic Composite Laminates Containing a Pin Loaded Hole. *J. Composite Materials*, **18**, 464-477 (1984).
5. I. H. Marshall, W. S. Arnold and J. Wood, Observation on Bolted Connections in Composite Structures. *Composite Structures*, **13**, 133-151 (1989).
6. H. S. Wang, C. L. Hung and F. K. Chang, Bearing Failure of Bolted Composite Joints Part I: Experiments. *J. Composite Materials* (submitted for publication).
7. P. A. Smith and K. J. Pascoe, The Effect of Stacking Sequence on the Bearing Strengths of Quasi-Isotropic Composite Laminates. *Composite Structures*, **6**, 1-20 (1986).
8. C. T. Sun and S. Li, Three-Dimensional Effective Elastic Constants for Thick Laminates. *J. Composite Materials*, **22**, 629-639 (1988).
9. C. T. Sun and J. L. Chen, A Simple Flow Rule for Characterizing Nonlinear Behaviors of Fiber Composites. *J. Composite Materials*, **23**, 1009-1020 (1989).
10. C. T. Sun and A. W. Jun, Compressive Strength of Unidirectional Fiber Composites with Matrix Non-linearity. *Composite Science and Technology*, **52**, 577-587 (1994).

APPLICATIONS
